

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF COMPONENTS OF LABOR ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Issues of labor education constitute the most important area of all educational work that must be carried out with preschoolers. Domestic pedagogical science has accumulated vast theoretical and practical experience in labor education, however, in recent years, due to changes in requirements for the content of education and the introduction of new educational standards, many previously existing guidelines and rules are being revised.

INTRODUCTION

Labor education and work activity are a necessary and essential condition for the development of children's independence. Children raised to work from an early age are distinguished by independence, organization, activity, neatness, and the ability to take care of themselves.

The problem of the development of labor activity in childhood, leading to the development of other personality traits, has been dealt with by many famous psychologists, teachers, as well as representatives of other related sciences. Labor activity is a special type of activity associated with the development of children's skills and abilities, the formation of psychological readiness and a responsible attitude to work.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The problem of the development of labor activity in childhood, leading to the development of other personality traits, has been dealt with by many famous psychologists, teachers, as well as representatives of other related sciences.

Comenius also highlighted a number of issues about children's independence. K.D. Ushinsky, P.Ya. Galperin, S.L. Rubenstein, L. and Bozovic., A.L. Wenger, as well as many others, made enormous contributions to the study of activity and independence in preschool children. Currently, scientists such as L.I. Antsyferova, R.S. Bure, G.A. Tsukerman, I.S. Yakimanskaya, N.V. Elizarov studied the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of independence in children. [8, p.34].

The importance of labor as a factor in the development of a child's personality is reflected in the history of Russian pedagogy: the works of P.P. Blonsky, N.K. Krupskaya, A.S. Makarenko, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, ST. Shatsky and others.

V.A. Sukhomlinsky has repeatedly noted that any work makes a person more creative, more joyful, intelligent, cultured, and educated. A very important point in the system of labor education V.A. Sukhomlinsky is the position that work allows you to most fully and clearly reveal the natural inclinations and inclinations of the child. [4;34] When analyzing a child's readiness for working life, you need to think not only about what he can give to society, but also about what work gives him personally. Every child has the inclinations of some abilities dormant. These inclinations are like gunpowder: to ignite, you need a spark. A child's abilities develop mainly in the context of activity.

A.S. Makarenko emphasized that in order to successfully solve the problems of labor education of preschool children, the creation of the necessary conditions is of paramount importance. A.S. Makarenko said that only with good organization does a child experience the joy of work, therefore, when organizing any activity, the primary tasks are clear planning of activities, organization of jobs, team formation and a clear distribution of responsibilities in accordance with the interests of the children. Labor activity should help improve the overall development of children, expand their interests, the emergence of the simplest forms of cooperation, the formation of such moral qualities as hard work, responsibility for the assigned work, and good advice. Good advice, kind help, support for even the smallest successes contribute to the development of positive personality traits. [9, p.67].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The important condition in labor education is knowledge of the characteristics of family education. Educators should know well how the work activities of their pupils are organized in the family; provide parents with the necessary assistance; they should constantly remember that only in close collaboration with the family can the task of raising a child at work be successfully solved.

Considering preschool age as the basic stage in the formation of personal qualities, the concept of lifelong education defines the essence of a new approach to preschool education, based on the principles of variable content, developmental pedagogy, and a preschooler's knowledge of the world through activities that interest him. At the same time, the concept draws attention to the development of personal qualities necessary for the further development of personality: curiosity, initiative, communication, creative imagination, arbitrariness.

However, the task of cultivating hard work is not put forward in the concept. Meanwhile, many authors (R.S. Bure, G.N. Godina, M.V. Krulekht, V.I. Loginova, T.A. Markova, V.G. Nechaeva, D.V. Sergeeva, etc.) note that a number of indicators of hard work (awareness of the goal of activity and perseverance in achieving it; willingness to complete the work begun; manifestation of an emotionally positive attitude towards work; adequate assessment of the results of activity; accuracy, diligence, careful attitude to the means and products of labor) are the most are successfully formed in preschool and primary school age. Their lack of formation at this age stage becomes an obstacle to educational and cognitive activity and subsequent adaptation to independent work.

Thus, scientists have made a significant contribution to the development of the problem of identifying the signs and components of hard work in preschool children. However, the problem of instilling hard work in preschoolers as a basic personality quality still remains insufficiently developed.

In the process of work, the child not only acquires a number of skills and abilities, but also learns in a practical way the properties of surrounding objects and phenomena.

To successfully solve the problems provided for by the program for the formation of positive attitudes in preschool children to various types of work and creativity, the creation of the necessary conditions is of paramount importance. Only with good organization does a child experience joy from work.

By getting involved in labor activities, the child radically changes his entire understanding of himself and the world around him. Self-esteem changes under the influence of the successes achieved by the child in work.

The educational process aimed at nurturing positive attitudes in preschool children towards various types of work and creativity will be successful when creating organizational, psychological and pedagogical conditions and should be built taking into account the following principles:

- supporting children's initiative in various activities.
- assistance and cooperation between children and adults, recognition of the child as a full participant in educational relations.
- building educational activities based on the individual characteristics of each child.
- full-fledged living by the child of all stages of childhood, enrichment (amplification) of child development.
- formation of cognitive interests and cognitive actions of the child in various types of activities.
- age adequacy of preschool education (compliance of conditions, requirements, methods with age and developmental characteristics).
- developmental education (systematic and consistent).
- novelty (use of the latest information technologies).
- integration (interpenetration of program sections and activities into each other, mutual combination of various tasks and educational technologies).

The work of a child has a number of distinctive features that distinguish it from the work of adults:

- a. The child does not create socially significant material values in his work.
- b. The work of preschool children is educational in nature, because satisfies the child's need for self-affirmation and knowledge of his own capabilities. Brings children closer to adults
- c. The work of preschool children is closely related to play.
- d. During the labor process, children often play out labor actions.
- e. Children's work does not have material reward and is situational and not obligatory, but the child's developing moral character suffers from its absence.
- f. All structural components of a child's work activity are only in development and necessarily require the help of an adult.

In preschool age, researchers identify the following types of work:

- self-care is work aimed at satisfying everyday needs: dressing and undressing, eating, sanitary and hygienic procedures. In older preschool age, this includes the ability to comb one's hair and decorate clothes.
- household work. It is aimed at maintaining cleanliness and order in the premises and area, helping adults in organizing routine processes.

Household work is aimed at serving peers, and therefore contains great opportunities for developing a caring attitude towards comrades.

In early preschool age, basic household and household skills are formed:

- Help set the table
- Organize toys, etc.

In older preschool age, household work becomes systematic and becomes the responsibility of those on duty.

The peculiarity of household work is the ability of children to organize it independently: select the necessary equipment, place it conveniently, put everything in order after work. This is what children should be taught.

The joy of work is a powerful educational force. During childhood, a child must deeply experience this noble feeling. Labor for the people is not only a vital necessity, without which human existence is impossible, but also a sphere of multifaceted manifestations of spiritual life, the spiritual wealth of the individual. The richness of human relationships is spread through work. It is impossible to cultivate a love of work if the child does not feel the beauty of this relationship. People see work as the most important means of self-expression and personal self-affirmation. Without work, a person becomes an empty place. An important educational task is that the sense of personal dignity and personal pride of each student is based on labor success.

The work of preschool children is the most important means of education. The entire process of raising children in kindergarten can and should be organized so that they learn to understand the benefits and necessity of work for themselves and for the team. Treating work with love and seeing joy in it is a necessary condition for the manifestation of a person's creativity and talents.

Labor has always been the basis for human life and culture.

At the same time, she called on teachers to take into account the capabilities of children, the characteristics of child labor, its originality, and its connection with play. The work activity of preschoolers includes the following components: motive, goal, work actions, planning, result.

Motive is the reason that encourages work. The motives may be different: the need for a positive assessment from adults; self-affirmation; need to communicate with adults; desire to learn something; social motives (to benefit others). Children, as a rule, have no desire to receive a material reward for their work. However, other motives are quite strong: to receive a positive assessment of one's actions from adults; will assert itself; enter into communication with an adult; benefit others (social motive).

A goal is something to strive for. The development of a goal setting proceeds from acceptance of the goal of work proposed by an adult to independent goal setting. The

conditions for the emergence and development of a goal in work are its accessibility to the child's understanding (why it needs to be done, what result to get), a visual algorithm of the expected result in the form of a drawing, and the feasibility of achieving it.

For a more distant goal, it is necessary to identify intermediate goals: plant seeds, water so that shoots appear, then buds, etc.

The ability to accept and then independently set the goal of work develops better if the child receives a result that is significant for him or for loved ones, which can be used in play or to satisfy other needs.

The child's actions are not purposeful, procedural in nature (i.e., the child enjoys the action itself, and not its result). Children master ways of acting to imitate an adult. In this regard, it is necessary to gradually develop in the child the ability to understand the purpose of his actions and the connection between the goal and the result.

Children of older preschool age set goals themselves in familiar situations (for example, making toys). But they can also be aware of individual goals (growing crops) that an adult sets and explains.

Labor actions are what is used to achieve the goal and achieve the result.

The child gradually masters work activities. The younger preschooler performs them under the direct guidance of an adult, when he is shown. An older preschooler already masters some work actions (can wash doll dishes, toys, sweep, wipe dust, etc.), and is able to learn work actions without direct demonstration, but by verbal explanation. Children develop individual labor skills, which they can perform freely, without the help of adults.

Planning is the ability to anticipate upcoming work.

Planning of work activity is an important component of work; it includes: organization of work, execution, control, evaluation.

In older preschool age, children often plan only the process of execution and forget about the organization of work, outlining only the main stages, but not the methods of execution.

Often there is also no provision for monitoring and evaluating one's own work. Verbal planning lags behind practical planning. Planning your activities should be specially taught, and all stages and methods of action should be discussed with the child. This teaches you to foresee the result of your work.

Initially, preliminary planning of children's work activities is carried out entirely by the teacher: he explains the purpose of the work, selects the necessary materials and tools, places them near each child in a certain order, shows or reminds the sequence of work actions. As they master labor actions and the labor process as a whole, children themselves move on to planning: before starting work, the child selects materials and tools, prepares the workplace and decides what he will do and in what order. The most difficult thing is for children to plan collective work: the distribution of work actions or responsibilities in a subgroup. However, it is formed only in older preschool age.

Mastery of planning contributes to a significant improvement in the quality of the child's work results.

The result is an indicator of completion of work, a factor that helps to cultivate children's interest in work. In accordance with the Federal State Educational Standard, the

result of each child's work is assessed as successful in relation to this type of work. The teacher's assessment is always positive and has an educational orientation. By organizing work activities, the teacher ensures the comprehensive development of children, helps them gain confidence in their abilities, promotes the formation of vital skills and abilities, instilling responsibility, independence and a value-based attitude towards their own work and the work of other people, setting each child up for success.

CONCLUSION

The problem of labor education is one of the most important in pedagogy and psychology.

The main goal of labor education is to develop a positive attitude towards work. It is implemented in 2 directions: familiarization with the work of adults, the formation of their ideas about the social significance of work and the organization of work activities of children, in the process of which work skills are formed, positive relationships, character traits, and work organization skills are cultivated.

Labor activity is a special type of activity associated with the development of children's skills and abilities, the formation of psychological readiness and a responsible attitude to work.

Labor activity in preschool age is the most important means of education, which can be used from a very early age, gradually complicating its content.

Labor activity consists of the following components - motive, goal, labor actions, planning, result. Their formation and development occurs with targeted pedagogical influence based on compliance with a number of principles.

The ascertaining experiment showed that the level of development of the components of work activity in children 4-5 years old is close to sufficient.

Based on the results of the ascertaining experiment, we developed a set of measures for the formation of components of work activity in children.

The developed set of measures, which includes various recommendations, can be used by educators in working with children 4-5 years old in order to form components of work activity.

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